

DETERMINATION OF NEW CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS OF SAADA (CYPERUS ROTUNDUS L) RHIZOMES

*¹Dr. Masheir Ebrahim Baleil, ²Dr. Mohammed Salem Abd Elfadil

*¹Assistant Professor College of Medical Sciences, Department of Phytochemistry, University of White Nile, Kosti Sudan.

²Associate Professor College of Education, Department of Chemistry, University of Imam Mahdi Kosti Sudan.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Masheir Ebrahim Baleil

Assistant Professor College of Medical Sciences, Department of Phytochemistry, University of White Nile, Kosti Sudan.

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ABSTRACT

To further purify the compounds the extract was absorbed on Polyamide gel. Bioactivity guided fractionation of *C. rotundus* led to isolation and characterization of six compounds by These compounds were isolated by using different chromatographic techniques and their structures were identified by(TLC method GCMS, UV, IR and ¹D NMR spectrum (C¹³ and ¹H-NMR) Moreover, GCMS analysis four known compounds(Stigmasterol(8.36%),4-Isopropyl-1,6-dimethyl-decahydronaphthalene (4,34%), 2H-Cyclopropanaphthalene-2-one(9.10%),1H-Cyclopropa{e} azulene (2.98%)) and two known compounds NMR analysis(3-isobutyl-Octahydro-naphthalene Tetradecahyl- pentaphenanthrenoate,).

INTRODUCTION

The essential oil was fractionated into fractions rich in hydrocarbons and oxygenated compounds using silica gel column chromatography (CC). These hydrocarbons were further separated through CC and TLC (thin-layer chromatography), resulting in isorotundene, (-)-cyperaa-2,4(15)-diene, norrotundene, cyperadione, and α -patchoulane-type sesquiterpene (Sonwa and König, 2001, Elezabeth and Arumugam 2014 Hikino,. and Aota 1998, Hsu, 1926, Jeong, Inagaki,. and Higuchi2000).^[1-4] The main class of compounds including sesquiterpenes, epoxides, ketones, monoterpenes, aliphatic alcohols, and aromatic compounds are identified in *C. rotundus* essential oils

(Sonwa and König, 2001).^[6] Gas chromatography (GC) and combined GC/MS (mass spectrometry) analysis identified 32 different components in the oil, forming about 98.6% of the total composition (Kilani., et al 2007).^[5]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Successive Extraction of the Roots

Weighed 100g of the rhizomes were successively extracted with petroleum ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate and methanol using Soxhlet Apparatus. Extraction was carried out for about 4 hours for petroleum ether, 12 hours for chloroform, and 8 hours for Ethyl acetate and 2 hours for methanol. Extract were then dishes and left under for to dryness. The yield percentage of each extract was calculated as follow.

Weight of extract X100/ weight of the crude powder plant.

Column Chromatography (CC)

Glass column of 90 cm length and 4 cm internal. Diameter and silica gel were used. Medicinal and Aromatic Plants Research Institute, Khartoum, Sudan.

Packing of the Column

A small piece of cotton was situated at the end of the column with glass rod. Column was filled with 450 g of silica and clouted with n hexane until the silica macerated. Air bubbles were removed by lapping the outer surface of column with rubber rod.

NMR spectroscopy

¹H NMR spectroscopy

The NMR spectrum of isolated products was obtained on a DRX-400 (1H 400 MHz) instrument from BRUKER (Karlsruhe, Germany). The internal standard was tetra methyl silane Proton chemical shifts are reported in ppm (δ) relative to internal Tetra methyl saline (TMS, δ 0.0 ppm), or with the solvent reference relative to TMS employed as an internal standard (CDCl₃, δ 7.26 ppm). Data are reported as follows: chemical shift (multiplicity [singlet (s), doublet (d), triplet (t), quartet (q), multiplet (m)], coupling constants [Hz], integration).

¹³C NMR spectroscopy

Carbon NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian 400 (100 MHz) or 500 (125 MHz) spectrometers with complete proton decoupling. In the Spectrum Devices Laboratory at King

Abdulaziz University in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. Carbon chemical shifts are reported in ppm (d) relative to TMS with the respective solvent resonance as the internal standard (CDCl₃, d 77.0 ppm). All NMR spectra were acquired at ambient temperature.

FT-IR spectroscopy

The infrared (IR) spectrum of the 5 and 6 extract was measured (as KBr discs) in the range of 400–4000 cm⁻¹ on FT-IR spectrophotometer (Shimadzu FTIR-8400 S, Kyoto, Japan). In the Spectrum Devices Laboratory at King Khalid University in abha, Saudi Arabia. The important IR bands, such as ν (C–N), ν (O–H), ν (CH), ν (C = C), ν (NH), ν (CO) and (CH) symmetric and asymmetric stretching, and stretching frequencies were studied to determine the presence of functional groups in the 5 and 6 extracts.

Polyamide Column

Column was prepared by macerated 90 g of polyamide power in about 25 ml distilled water for one hour then was poured in the column and kept till complete homogeneous. Extract after mixed with silica gel was poured at the top of the column and eluted with (water, methanol, ethyl acetate and chloroform). The graduation of solvent was 20% in each time. fraction was collected in 25 ml test tube and monitored with thin layer chromatography on silica gel using n-butanol: acetic acid: water (12 :3 :5) as solvent system. The plates were detected under UV lamp and sprayed with vanillin sulphuric acid plates containing the similar spots were combined together and allowed to dry then weight.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fraction of Column Chromatography

Fraction of column chromatography of the *C.rotundus* Powdered extracted from rhizomes by using different solvents as (methanol, ethyl acetate, chloroform and petroleum ether).

(methanol: MeOH, ethyl acetate: E.A, chloroform: CHCl₃ and petroleum ether: P.E, Fr. No: Fraction number and Wt.: weight). Column chromatography is method used to purify individual chemical compounds. It is often used for preparative applications on scales from micrograms to kilograms. the fraction done by solvent eluent using CHCl₃ and MeOH showed good weight and good percentage more than that which used other solvent eluent as E.A. Solvent eluent mixture MeOH and E.A mixture gave high yield and percentage (2.566, 23.32%) and (2.369, 21.54%) respectively in fraction number (183-188) and (189-195). Fractions which having high weights were Fraction 71-119 (12,944 g) and Fraction 13 (2,566

g) and 14(2,369) while the Fractions which have least weight are Fraction 25 (0.051 g) and fraction 26 (0.001 g).

Table (1): Polyamide column fraction.

fraction	Weight	Limit	Elution
1	0.04g	1-80	Water
2	0.032g	81-100	Water- Methanol
3	0.172g	101-106	Methanol- ethyl acetate
4	0. 62g	107-126	Chloroform
5	0. 45g	127-138	Chloroform-P.Ether

Table (1) five main extractions were purified by method involving polyamide column chromatography. The extraction/separation technique was validated using TLC method. Solvent eluent mixture MeOH and E.A mixture gave high yield (0.172g), CHCL₃ (0. 62g) and -P.E (0. 45g) respectively in fraction number (101-106), (107-126) and (127-138). These weights were suitable for the rest of the analysis techniques. of {9:1}

Structure Elucidation of compound MH-5

The structure of the compound is given below:

IR ν_{\max} (KBr): The FT-IR spectra exhibited bands 2995, 2924, 1729, 1717, 1360, 1241, 1149, 500, and 402 cm^{-1} from which the presence of alkanes, alkenes, hydroxyl and carboxyl groups was inferred. The IR spectrum of the compound included a diagnostic peak at 2995 cm^{-1} . Was assigned to aromatic C–H stretching. The peak appearing at 2924 cm^{-1} was assigned to CH₃– and –CH₂– stretching (alkanes). The peak appearing at 1717 cm^{-1} was assigned to C = C stretching (alkene). The peak appearing at 1241 cm^{-1} was assigned to ether. The peak appearing at 1149 cm^{-1} was assigned to CH₃. The peak appearing at 500 cm^{-1} was assigned to alkene and the peak appearing at 402 cm^{-1} was assigned to alkyl halide. Structure compound MH-5 was elucidated by ¹³CNMR and ¹HNMR. Spectra showed the presence of four terminal methyl's at δ , 1.25, 1.41, 1.33 and 2, 09 are assigned for H₁₁', H₁₂, H₁₅, and H₁₆"', respectively. two signals at δ 6.59, and 6.60 and due to olefinic protons are assigned for H₃' and H₄', respectively ¹H-NMR data also showed five multiplets signals attributed to methylene protons at δ 1.28, 1.42, 2.00, 2.15, and 2.95 are assigned to H₁, H₂, H₇, H₉ and H₁₃ respectively. Four methine signals at δ 3.64, 4.29, 1.29 and 0.88 are assigned to H₅, H₆, H₈ and H₁₄ respectively.

¹³CNMR data revealed clear two carbons contributed in the double bonds at δ 123.53 and 124.13 are assigned to C₃ and C₄ respectively. ¹³CNMR data showed intense signals

attributed to four methine signals at δ 33.70, 29.67, 30.20 and 14.14 (olefinic carbon), are assigned to C₅, C₆, C₈ and C₁₄ respectively. Five methylenes signals at δ 28.98, 31.45, 23.19, 29.38 and 115.91 are assigned to C₁, C₂, C₇, C₉ and C₁₃ respectively. Four methyl groups at δ 26.71, 22.71, 31.63 and 31.94 assigned to C₁₁, C₁₂, C₁₅ and C₁₆ respectively. Data obtained from ¹H and ¹³C spectrum showed that this compound has molecular formula of C₁₆H₂₈ corresponding to MW equal to 220. On the basis of these evidences the structure of MH-5 has been established as C₁₆H₂₈.

3-Isobutyl-1,4a-dimethyl-1,2,3,4,4a,5,6,8a-octahydro-

Fig (3): 3-isobutyl-Octahydro- naphthale.

Structure Elucidation of compound MH-6

The structure of the compound is given below:

IR ν_{\max} (KBr): The FT-IR spectra exhibited bands 3250, 3000, 2950, 2858, 1729, 1486, 1366, 1273, 1241, 1149, 755 and 500 cm^{-1} from which the presence of alkanes, alkenes, hydroxyl and carboxyl groups was inferred. The IR spectrum of the compound) included a diagnostic peak at 3250 cm^{-1} hydroxyl group. 3000 cm^{-1} was assigned to aromatic C–H stretching. The peak appearing at 2950 cm^{-1} was assigned to CH₃– and –CH₂– stretching (alkanes). The peak appearing at 2858 cm^{-1} was assigned to OH (alcohol) symmetric stretching. The peak appearing at 1729 cm^{-1} was assigned to C = C stretching (alkene). The peak appearing at 1486 cm^{-1} was assigned to COO⁻¹ stretching (fatty acid ester). The peak appearing at 1366 cm^{-1} was assigned to C–O group. The peak appearing at 1241 cm^{-1} was assigned to ether. The peak appearing at 1149 cm^{-1} was assigned to CH₃. The peak appearing at 755 cm^{-1} was assigned to alkene and the peak appearing at 500 cm^{-1} was assigned to alkyl halide.

Compound MH-6 was identified by NMR. The ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral. The ¹H NMR spectrum showed proton appeared as triplet of and three olefinic protons appeared at δ 5.06 (H₁₁, m), and δ 4.71 (H₂₀, m) five methyl groups resonating at δ 1.25, 1.28, 1.57, 2.09, and 2.13 ppm are assigned H₁₈, H₁₉, H₂₂, H₂₃, and H₂₅ respectively. ¹H-NMR data also showed multiplets signals attributed to methylene protons at δ 2.00, 2.58, 2.61, 2.88, 4.20, 7.52,

and 7.69 are assigned H₁, H₂, H₄, H₈, H₉, H₁₄, and H₁₅ respectively. Spectra showed the presence of five terminal methine at δ 0.83, 0.91, 1.41, 1.42 and 2.04 are assigned H₅, H₆, H₇, H₁₃, and H₁₇ respectively. one signals at oxygenated methylene region at δ 3.00 are assigned H₃.

¹³CNMR data showed intense signals attributed to two quaternary carbons including ester carbonyl group at δ 165.3 is assigned to C₂₄ two carbons contributed in the double bonds at δ 129.75 and 130.93 are assigned to C₁₁ and C₁₂ respectively. ¹³CNMR data showed intense signals attributed to seven methane signals at δ 76.87 (attached to oxygen), δ 38.73, 37.11, 31.94, 31.63, 23.75 and 124.09 (olefinic carbon), are assigned to C₃, C₅, C₆, C₇, C₁₃, C₁₆ and C₂₀ respectively. Seven methylene's signals at δ 22.71, 23.00, 28.93, 29.38, 30.20, 30.71, and 115.91, are assigned to C₁, C₂, C₄, C₈, C₉, C₁₄ and C₁₅ respectively. Five methyl groups at δ 13.74, 14.14, 19.20, 19.20, and 14.07, assigned to C₁₈, C₁₉, C₂₂, C₂₃, and C₂₅ respectively. On the bases of these evidences the structure of MH-6- has been established as with molecular formula C₂₅H₃₇O₂, the identification of the MH-6- was confirmed by comparing its chromatographic and spectral data (TLC and NMR) with reference sample.

Acetic acid 5,14-dimethyl-15-(2-methyl-propenyl)-
2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,13,14,15,16,17-tetradecahydro-1H-
cyclopenta[a]phenanthren-2-yl ester

Fig (6): Tetradecahyl-penta phenanthrenoate.

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